

ARTICLE CORRECTION

Correction to Pippa Smart's viewpoint, "Dealing with difficult authors". DOI: 10.3897/ese.2020.e52201

DOI: 10.3897/ese.2020.e58964

In this article the author's competing interests were not declared. This has been corrected in the online article, DOI: 10.3897/ese.2020.e52201.